

Review

Non-occupational exposure to cadmium and breast cancer: A comprehensive and critical review

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ABSTRACT

Breast cancer (BC) is a multifactorial disease with unresolved etiology. Environmental pollutants, primarily trace metals, play a pivotal role in the pathophysiological cascade of malignant tumors, including BC. In this up-to-date review, we comprehensively and critically examined the relationship between cadmium (Cd) and BC. For this purpose, peer-reviewed studies from relevant databases (PubMed, SCOPUS, and Cochrane Library) over the last 40 years were retrieved and analyzed. We found that *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies strongly support the view that Cd has harmful effects on breast health. According to the human studies, we found that Cd could be responsible for the development and progression of malignant breast tumors due to markedly higher levels in clinical matrices of cases (whole blood, urine, breast tissue, keratin materials) than in clinical matrices of controls. Cadmium does not appear to affect BC density. In contrast, Cd has been found to have a detrimental effect on sex hormones, disrupting the balance of estrogen and androgen. We found that studies looking at dietary Cd intake and BC risk generally (without measuring urine or blood Cd) do not support the association between dietary Cd intake and BC risk. In notable contrast, studies looking at dietary Cd intake and BC risk by measuring Cd in urine or blood generally support this association. The effect of airborne Cd on BC risk was weak, but in favor of specific histological forms, primarily ER-/PR- invasive tubular breast carcinomas. Regardless of the intake route of Cd into the body, it can be concluded that Cd has a harmful effect on breast health. However, well-designed longitudinal, mechanistic, meta-analytic, and other studies are urgently needed to confirm the exact role of environmental Cd in breast carcinogenesis.

Abbreviations: AKT, Protein kinase B; Bcl-2, B-cell lymphoma 2; CAT, Catalase; Cd²⁺, Cadmium ion; EGFR, Epidermal growth factor receptor; EMT, Epithelial–mesenchymal transition; ER α , Estrogen receptor alpha; ERE, Estrogen response element; ERK, Extracellular signal-regulated kinase; GSH, Glutathione; HO-1, Heme oxygenase 1; IGF, Insulin-like growth factor; MAPK, Mitogen-activated protein kinase; MEK, MAPK/ERK kinase; MTOR, Mammalian target of rapamycin; NOX1, NADPH oxidase 1; PI3K, Phosphoinositide 3-kinase; ROS, reactive oxygen species; SOD, superoxide dismutase; TNBC, triple-negative breast cancer.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Cadmium – a brief overview

Cadmium (Cd) is one of the most common environmental pollutants (Lappano et al., 2017). It is a toxic, heavy, and non-biodegradable metal (Khan et al., 2022). Cadmium is a non-essential metal for human health (Suhani et al., 2021). The World Health Organization (WHO) and the US Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry (ATSDR) rank Cd among the 10 chemicals of greatest concern to human health (ATSDR, 2017). According to the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), Cd is classified as a Group 1 carcinogen to humans (IARC, 2018). So far, long-term exposure to Cd has been linked to lung, prostate, breast, colon, and hepatocellular carcinoma in humans (Joseph, 2009; Li et al., 2023), although the most convenient epidemiological and experimental evidence relates to lung cancer (ATSDR, 2017; Rasin et al., 2025). For the long-term link between Cd exposure and the aforementioned cancers, the question of the exact doses that lead to carcinogenesis remains unresolved (Cui et al., 2021).

In general, Cd is introduced into the body through ingestion (food, drinking water) and inhalation (polluted air and optionally through tobacco smoke) (Li et al., 2023). The main route of ingestion of Cd into the body is through food; dietary intake accounts for approximately 90 % of total Cd exposure in the non-smoking population (Zhao et al., 2023). Cadmium intake through drinking water is negligible (< 1 µg/L), with the exception of places near polluted areas (≥ 10 µg/L) (Divekar et al., 2020). High levels of Cd have been found in shellfish, crustaceans, cephalopods, offal (liver and kidney), oilseeds, cocoa beans, and certain wild mushrooms (Hossain et al., 2019; Genchi et al., 2020). Plant-derived foods, depending on the percentage of Cd contamination in the soil, contain higher levels of this metal than milk, meat, eggs, and dairy products; thus, rice and wheat, green leafy vegetables, carrots, potatoes, and celery can contain higher levels of Cd than other plant-derived foods (Genchi et al., 2020; Kubier et al., 2019). Consequently, vegans, vegetarians, and strict shellfish consumers consume higher amounts of Cd than people on regular diet/omnivores (Byrne et al., 2013; Genchi et al., 2020). The European Food Safety Agency (EFSA) has reduced the previously safe intake of Cd proposed by the WHO/International Programme on Chemical Safety (WHO/IPCS) and set a new one of 2.5 µg/kgbw per week, based on Cd-induced nephrotoxicity (EFSA, 2009; Hartwig, 2013). This guideline is proposed to keep urinary Cd below 1.0 µg/L in 95 % of the population up to 50 years of age (Florez-Garcia, 2023). Details on daily dietary intake of Cd by country are given in Table 1.

Approximately 5–10 % of ingested Cd is absorbed and the efficiency of absorption is higher in individuals with iron (Fe), calcium (Ca), and/or zinc (Zn) deficiencies (Davidova et al., 2024). Since women have lower levels of Fe in their bodies, they are more susceptible to the toxic effects of Cd than men. On the other hand, dermal uptake of Cd into the body is negligible (Pokharel and Wu, 2023). The main inhalation routes of Cd entry into the body are polluted air and tobacco smoking (Jomova et al., 2025). Still, below 10 % of total exposure occurs through inhalation of Cd-contaminated air (Zhao et al., 2023). Ten to 50 % of inhaled Cd is absorbed, depending on the size of the dust particles (Charkiewicz et al., 2023). Depending on the type of tobacco, a cigarette contains 1–2 µg of Cd. A person who smokes 20 cigarettes a day will absorb about 1 µg of Cd, but the estimated daily intake of Cd from one pack of cigarettes can be up to 4 µg (Mezynska and Brzóska, 2018; Wróblewski et al., 2024). Cadmium levels in the kidneys of non-smokers (15–20 µg/g) are approximately two times lower than in smokers (30–40 µg/g) (Byrne et al., 2013). Similarly, Cd levels in the blood of smokers were 2–3 times higher than in blood of nonsmokers (Zečević et al., 2025). Specifically, blood Cd levels in the general unexposed population are 0.4–1.0 µg/L for non-smokers and 1.4–4 µg/L for smokers, while notably higher blood levels have been reported for environmental and occupational exposures (Repić et al., 2020).

Table 1

Dietary Cd intake (µg/day) in general populations across the globe, by country.

Country	Dietary Cd intake (µg/day)		Year	Ref.
	Mean	95th percentile		
Bangladesh	34.6	-	2008–2009	Al-Rmalli et al. (2012)
Belgium*	16.1	29.0	2003–2011	EFSA (2012)
Canada	13.2	-	2007	Health Canada (2007)
Chile	18.1	-	2012	Muñoz et al. (2017)
China	17.3	-	2016–2019	Zhao et al. (2023)
Czech Republic*	13.8	24.9	2003–2011	EFSA (2012)
Denmark*	13.5	21.2	2003–2011	EFSA (2012)
Finland*	13.0	22.5	2003–2011	EFSA (2012)
France*	15.3	26.8	2003–2011	EFSA (2012)
Germany*	12.9	22.4	2003–2011	EFSA (2012)
Hungary*	16.2	32.1	2003–2011	EFSA (2012)
Ireland*	16.9	27.4	2003–2011	EFSA (2012)
Italy*	18.9	41.2	2003–2011	EFSA (2012)
Japan	26.4	-	2001–2005	Itoh et al. (2014)
Korea	14.5	35.3	2001–2003	Kim and Wolt (2011)
Latvia*	14.7	28.5	2003–2011	EFSA (2012)
Lebanon	15.8	-	2008	Nasreddine et al. (2010)
Netherlands*	14.4	23.7	2003–2011	EFSA (2012)
Spain*	19.1	38.1	2003–2011	EFSA (2012)
Sweden*	15.2	26.8	2003–2011	EFSA (2012)
United Kingdom*	14.2	23.0	2003–2011	EFSA (2012)
United States	4.6	-	2006–2013	Kim et al. (2018)

Units were converted to µg/day based on a body weight of 60 kg.

* Mean restricted values (values <LOR represented as LOR/2).

Cadmium primarily accumulates in the kidneys, with the S1 segment of the proximal tubule being the main target of Cd deposition (Doccioli et al., 2024). As a result, Fanconi syndrome can develop (a defect in the proximal tubules that leads to malabsorption of numerous substances that are normally absorbed) (Keefe and Bokhari, 2025). Among other target organs, bones are prone to Cd deposition. The well-described “itai-itai” disease (endemic chronic Cd poisoning from contaminated rice in Japan) is an excellent example of the negative effects of Cd on the bone matrix (osteomalacia with or without osteoporosis) (Zhang et al., 2025).

Cadmium can impair renal clearance, resulting in a long half-life in the body (10–30 years, or longer); thus, the level of Cd in urine reflects exposure in the body proportional to the biological half-life (Genchi et al., 2020; Mohammadian-Hafshejani et al., 2024). The half-life of Cd in the blood is 75–128 days, but this half-life primarily represents deposition in organs rather than removal from the body (Bernhoft, 2013). Consequently, Cd levels in whole blood are weaker markers of body burden than are levels in other tissues, and generally reflect recent exposure (Stojsavljević et al., 2024). In contrast, urine is a suitable clinical sample for assessing lifetime Cd exposure (Vacchi-Suzzi et al., 2016). Hair and nails can be suitable clinical matrices for assessing monthly Cd exposure (Lotah et al., 2021), but these biological materials suffer from external contamination during sample preparation for Cd analysis (Jursa et al., 2018).

Cadmium acts as an endocrine-disrupting chemical (EDC) due to its deposition in reproductive organs, disruption of the hormonal system, its indirect causation of oxidative stress, and its interference with normal reproduction (Sabir et al., 2019; Macedo et al., 2023). Cadmium is an estrogen-mimicking metal; the ionic form of cadmium, Cd²⁺, acts as a metalloestrogen, preventing 17β-estradiol from binding to the receptor (Strumylaitė et al., 2010; Yang et al., 2015). Cadmium is one of the best-known metalloestrogens, due to its high affinity for the estrogen receptor α isoform (ERα), thereby mimicking the action of endogenous estrogen (at lower doses, while at higher doses it has antiestrogenic

effects), and its ability to displace Zn from the ER Zn domain (Buha Djordjevic et al., 2021; Psaltis et al., 2024). Cadmium can interfere with the activity of several antioxidant enzymes and lead to oxidative stress. In fact, oxidative stress is the main mechanism through which Cd disrupts the body's homeostasis (Branca et al., 2020). Cadmium toxicity is reduced by the expression of small cysteine-rich proteins, metallothioneins (MTs) (Genchi et al., 2020; Souza-Arroyo et al., 2022). Metallothioneins are Zn-concentrating proteins that act as free radical scavengers (Qu and Zheng, 2024). Cells that do not express MTs are more sensitive or even more resistant to the harmful effects of Cd than cells that express them (Peana et al., 2022). Details about metal-estrogenic and other molecular roles of Cd are provided in Section 2.

1.2. Breast cancer – a brief overview

Breast cancer is the most common malignant tumor diagnosed in women and the second most common cause of cancer death among women across the globe (Harbeck et al., 2019). It is a complex, heterogeneous disease with unique epidemiological patterns (Xiong et al., 2025). Breast cancer patients account for approximately 36 % of all oncology patients (Smolarz et al., 2022). Breast cancer accounted for about 11.7 % of new cases in 2020, which corresponds to more than 1 in 10 new cancer cases per year (Menon et al., 2025). The incidence of BC increases markedly with age, and the median age of women at the time of diagnosis is 61 years (Menon et al., 2025). More developed countries have a higher incidence of BC than countries with moderate or low development, but lower mortality rates (Bray et al., 2024; Xiong et al., 2025).

Breast cancer usually arises in the ductal epithelium (ductal carcinoma) or in the breast lobules (lobular carcinoma) (Loibl et al., 2021). Both ductal and lobular carcinomas can be *in situ* (the cancer is still present where it first appeared and has not spread to nearby tissues). Both invasive ductal and invasive lobular breast carcinomas mean that the cancer has spread to the tissues around them (Obeagu and Obeagu, 2024). Therefore, ductal and lobular carcinomas are the most frequent histopathological forms of invasive BC, and they account for 50–75 % and 10–15 % of all invasive BCs, respectively. Other forms of BC (mucinous, tubular, medullary carcinomas, etc.) occur less frequently

Fig. 1. Overview of BC Risk Factors. This schematic illustration presents an overview of well-established risk factors contributing to BC development. Non-modifiable factors include female sex, increasing age, personal or family history of BC, genetic predisposition, and early menarche or late menopause. Modifiable factors encompass reproductive history (nulliparity, lack of breastfeeding, or late age at first childbirth), exogenous hormone exposure (contraceptives or HRT), lifestyle-related factors (obesity, alcohol, smoking), and radiation or environmental exposures, including contact with EDC.

(Pareja et al., 2025).

The risk factors for BC are shown in Fig. 1. In general, risk factors for BC are sex (approximately 1:8 for women and 1:1000 for men), age (women over 50 years are more susceptible than women under 50 years, although the incidence rate in premenopausal adult women between 20 and 49 years of age has almost doubled in the last 30 years), personal history (a primary malignant tumor in one breast increases the risk of its occurrence in the other breast), family history (first-degree relatives of BC sufferers have a 2–3 times higher risk), genetic mutations (BRCA1 and BRCA2 genes, although genetic burden only causes up to 10 % of all BC cases), reproductive status (endogenous estrogen increases the risk, as does the onset of menarche before age 12, first live birth after age 30, nulliparity, and menopause after age 55), use of exogenous sex hormones (contraception in premenopausal women or hormone replacement therapy/HRT in postmenopausal women), radiation (X- and γ -radiation), environmental or occupational exposure (mostly women who work shifts in industry, flight attendants, nurses, etc.), and increased obesity (Weiderpass et al., 2011; Łukasiewicz et al., 2021; Brito-Marcelino et al., 2021; Roheel et al., 2023; Løyland et al., 2024; Menon et al., 2025).

Breast cancer is diagnosed through a physical examination, breast imaging, and tissue biopsy (Barba et al., 2021). Immunohistochemistry is pivotal in determining hormone receptors for estrogen (ER+ or ER-), progesterone (PR+ or PR-), and human epidermal growth factor receptor (HER2) (HER2+ or HER2-) (Williams et al., 2009). Hormone receptor-positive tumors are less aggressive, so patient survival rates are higher with adequate therapy. In contrast, HER-2 tumors are more aggressive and with a poor prognosis, particularly if not treated with targeted therapy (Wei, 2023; Menon et al., 2025). Additionally, BC is classified according to the TNM classification system, which groups cases into four stage categories based on the size of the primary tumor (T), the status of regional lymph nodes (N), and whether there are distant metastases (M) (Rakha et al., 2023). Breast cancer treatment includes surgery, chemotherapy, radiation, hormone therapy, and/or immunotherapy. Treatment is now individualized, depending on histology, stage (I-IV), tumor markers, etc. (Wang and Wu, 2023). In-depth details on the diagnosis and treatment of BC are beyond the scope of this paper and can be found elsewhere (Wang and Wu, 2023; Menon et al., 2025).

1.3. Study objectives

In this review, we aimed to summarize information concerning the impact of Cd on BC from several perspectives: 1) describing the molecular basis of Cd toxicity in BC (*in vitro* and *in vivo* studies), 2) examining potential differences in Cd levels between human cases and controls in different clinical matrices (whole blood, serum/plasma, urine, breast tissue, hair), 3) examining the effects of Cd on BC density and reproductive hormones, and 4) highlighting the exposure to Cd from food and air on BC risk. To conduct the most comprehensive analysis possible, we extracted the most relevant peer-reviewed studies from the last 40 years from major databases (PubMed, SCOPUS, and Cochrane Library). Only studies that highlighted non-occupational (environmental) Cd exposure and its impact on breast health were considered. The impact of occupational exposure to Cd in the workplace is not the focus of this review. In addition, all enrolled studies were critically analyzed to highlight strengths and weaknesses, with the aim of making future research as accurate as possible.

2. Molecular basis of Cd toxicity in BC

The utilization of *in vitro* models has been pivotal in elucidating the cellular and molecular mechanisms underpinning Cd-induced oncogenesis. Given the clinicopathological heterogeneity of BC, a diverse array of cell lines has been employed, each representing distinct molecular subtypes and enabling researchers to capture the complex impact

of Cd exposure across different tumor phenotypes. Investigations using controlled experimental setups have demonstrated that this pervasive environmental pollutant can modulate breast epithelial cells through a constellation of multiple interconnected, non-mutually exclusive mechanisms, including oxidative stress induction, epigenetic remodeling, endocrine mimicry, aberrant signaling pathway activation, dysregulation of apoptosis, immune and inflammatory perturbations, as well as impairments in DNA repair mechanisms and cell adhesion dynamics (Tarhonska et al., 2022; Aquino et al., 2012). Collectively, these multifaceted effects likely contribute to all phases of neoplastic transformation and tumor development, reinforcing the notion that Cd is an important environmental carcinogen in BC etiology (Zimta et al., 2019).

Two of the most extensively studied models in Cd-related BC research are MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines, both derived from pleural effusions of breast carcinoma patients (Luparello, 2021). MCF-7 cells, classified as ER+ and PR- adenocarcinoma, serve as a well-established model for hormone-responsive BC (Levenson and Jordan, 1997). These cells exhibit a strong dependence on estrogen signaling for proliferation, making them particularly relevant for investigating Cd's metalloestrogenic activity. Conversely, MDA-MB-231 cells, representative of triple-negative BC (TNBC) with basal-like characteristics, lack estrogen and progesterone receptor expression and harbor a p53 mutation (codon 280, exon 8), rendering them an aggressive, hormone-independent model (Huovinen et al., 2011). Their unique molecular profile enables the investigation of Cd-driven oxidative stress and apoptosis resistance mechanisms, which are often hallmarks of TNBC progression. Beyond malignant breast epithelial cells, HB2 immortalized non-tumorigenic mammary epithelial cells provide a crucial comparative model for assessing Cd's carcinogenic potential at early stages of tumorigenesis (Caradonna and Luparello, 2014).

Recognizing the importance of estrogen signaling in breast oncopathology, particular attention has been directed toward environmental agents capable of mimicking or disrupting endocrine pathways. Among these, Cd is the most extensively studied metalloestrogen, capable of activating the ER α , in the absence of its endogenous ligand, thereby eliciting both genomic and non-genomic estrogenic signaling cascades in hormone receptor-positive BC lines (Stoica et al., 2000). Mechanistically, Cd is proposed to interact with the ligand-binding domain (LBD) of ER α , displacing estradiol in a noncompetitive manner and triggering ER dimerization, nuclear translocation, and subsequent transcriptional activation of estrogen-responsive genes (Siewit et al., 2010). This activation results in the upregulation of progesterone receptor and pS2, classical markers of estrogenic stimulation (Garcia-Morales et al., 1994). Furthermore, Cd can substitute for Zn in the DNA-binding domain (DBD) of ER α , potentially modifying its binding to estrogen response elements (EREs) and altering downstream transcriptional activity (Predki and Sarkar, 1994). Beyond its effects on nuclear ER α , Cd engages non-genomic signaling through membrane-associated ER α and G-protein coupled estrogen receptor (GPER), triggering rapid phosphorylation of ERK1/2 and PI3K/Akt. This signaling cascade converges on key oncogenic targets such as c-myc, c-fos, and c-jun, driving proliferation and survival in ER-positive BC cells. Interestingly, in ER α -negative but GPER-positive SKBR3 cells, Cd induces mitogenic activity via GPER-mediated ERK1/2 activation, suggesting an alternative, non-classical estrogenic signaling mechanism that broadens its endocrine-disrupting potential (Yu et al., 2010; Liu et al., 2008). The metalloestrogenic effects of Cd are highly context-dependent, as TNBC models, which predominantly express ER β or lack ER expression, do not display similar proliferative responses. Instead, Cd selectively downregulates astrocyte-elevated gene-1 (AEG-1, also known as metadherin, MTDH) in TNBC cells, influencing NF- κ B signaling and stress response pathways (Luparello et al., 2012). These findings underscore the molecular specificity of Cd's estrogenic influence, revealing distinct functional consequences in hormone-responsive versus hormone-independent BC subtypes. Beyond its role as a metalloestrogen, Cd has been implicated in the direct malignant

transformation of non-tumorigenic breast epithelial cells, reinforcing its oncogenic potential through mechanisms that extend beyond ER activation. Prolonged exposure of MCF-10A cells, an immortalized but non-malignant breast epithelial model, to low micromolar concentrations of Cd (2.5 μ mol/L) precipitates a gradual acquisition of neoplastic hallmarks, including loss of contact inhibition, heightened invasive capacity, and enhanced secretion of matrix metalloproteinase-9 (MMP-9), a key effector of extracellular matrix remodeling. At the molecular level, Cd-driven transformation is accompanied by global DNA hypomethylation, coupled with the overexpression of oncogenic drivers, such as c-myc and k-ras, indicative of profound epigenetic deregulation fostering an aggressive cellular phenotype. The resulting Cd-transformed breast epithelial (CTBE) cells exhibit a basal-like molecular signature, characterized by ER α and HER2 negativity, CK5 and p63 upregulation, and stem-like proliferative traits. The tumorigenic potential of CTBE cells extends beyond *in vitro* observations, as xenografting into immunocompromised mice leads to the formation of invasive, metastatic anaplastic carcinoma (Benbrahim-Tallaa et al., 2009) (Fig. 2).

The metalloestrogenic properties of Cd are further substantiated by *in vivo* studies demonstrating its ability to mimic endogenous estrogens in whole-animal models. In female Sprague-Dawley ovariectomized rats, a single intraperitoneal dose of Cd (5 μ g/kg) induced endometrial proliferation, increased uterine weight, and upregulated PR and complement component C3, mimicking estradiol-driven transcriptional activation. Similarly, Cd promoted mammary gland remodeling, characterized by enhanced ductal branching, alveolar budding, and induction of casein and whey acidic protein, suggesting a role in hormonally mediated differentiation. Beyond postnatal exposure, *in utero* Cd administration (0.5–5 μ g/kg) elicited early pubertal onset and persistent mammary epithelial expansion in female offspring, paralleling the developmental impact of estrogens (Johnson et al., 2003). Furthermore, age-dependent differences in Cd's influence on mammary morphology have been observed. In prepubertal models, sub-chronic (short exposure period, up to 90 days) Cd exposure was found to disrupt mammary ductal growth and reduce the number of terminal end buds, whereas in adult animals, Cd's estrogenic effects persisted, promoting lobuloalveolar development and extensive ductal branching, independent of the steroidal milieu. Interestingly, co-administration of melatonin partially attenuated Cd's estrogenic effects, suggesting a potential protective role of this indoleamine against Cd-induced endocrine disruption. The ability of melatonin to modulate Cd bioavailability varied depending on hormonal status, reducing Cd retention in ovariectomized animals while exacerbating its accumulation in intact mice. These findings underscore the complex interplay between exogenous endocrine disruptors and endogenous regulatory mechanisms, with potential implications for environmental and occupational exposure risks (Alonso-González et al., 2007). Expanding beyond classical estrogenic pathways, evidence suggests that Cd's endocrine-disrupting effects could not be solely mediated through direct ER activation. In an ERE-luciferase reporter mouse model, Cd exposure (5–500 μ g/kg) induced uterine epithelial proliferation without significantly altering uterine weight, vaginal opening, or classical ERE-driven transcription, suggesting a selective and non-genomic estrogenic effect. Instead, Cd activated mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) cascades, as evidenced by increased Mdm2 and Erk1/2 phosphorylation in hepatic tissues, contrasting with the robust ERE-mediated effects observed with ethinylestradiol. These findings suggest that Cd exerts selective estrogenic effects through alternative mechanisms in this mouse model, bypassing direct ER binding and engaging mitogenic cascades that converge on oncogenic transcriptional programs. Such non-classical signaling routes could contribute to Cd's broader endocrine-disrupting potential, influencing estrogen-sensitive tissues even in the absence of direct ER activation (Ali et al., 2010).

Unlike transition metals, Cd does not participate in direct redox cycling, but it profoundly disrupts cellular redox homeostasis through

Fig. 2. Schematic Representation of Molecular Mechanisms Underlying Cd-Induced Carcinogenesis in Experimental BC Models. MCF-7 cells (ER⁺/PR⁻), MDA-MB-231 cells (triple-negative BC, TNBC), and HB2 immortalized non-tumorigenic mammary epithelial cells represent distinct experimental platforms for evaluating Cd's estrogenic and non-estrogenic actions. Upon exposure, Cd enters the cell and initiates a cascade of intracellular perturbations, including oxidative stress, mitochondrial dysfunction, Ca dyshomeostasis, and dysregulated ER α signaling. Its estrogenic effects and endocrine-disrupting activity are mediated via both classical (genomic) and non-classical (non-genomic) ER α pathways, ultimately converging on the activation of PI3K/AKT/mTOR and MAPK/ERK signaling cascades, which coordinate transcriptional, proliferative, and survival responses. In the nucleus, Cd promotes the upregulation of four major groups of genes: (1) pro-inflammatory mediators (NF- κ B, TNF- α , IL-6/8/10, AEG-1/MTDH), (2) oncogenes and EMT-associated transcription factors (c-Fos, c-Jun, SNAIL1, MMP-9, β -catenin, vimentin), (3) cell cycle and survival regulators (c-Myc, Bcl-2, cyclin D1/E1, PLP2), and (4) redox and detoxification-related genes (GSTP1, GSTO1, HO-1, GPX1, SOD1, CAT, metallothioneins MT-1A/1E/1X/2 A). In parallel, Cd modulates integrin-mediated focal adhesion signaling via FAK/Src/Rac, and perturbs Ca/calmodulin dynamics, further influencing apoptotic control through caspase pathways. The figure also illustrates the neoplastic transformation of HB2 cells following chronic Cd exposure and the subsequent formation of aggressive tumors in xenograft animal models, supporting Cd's *in vivo* tumorigenic potential. *Abbreviations:* AEG-1/MTDH, Astrocyte-elevated gene-1/Metadherin; AKT, Protein kinase B; Bcl-2, B-cell lymphoma 2; Ca²⁺, Calcium ion; CaMKII, Calcium/calmodulin-dependent protein kinase II; CAT, Catalase; Cd²⁺, Cadmium ion; c-Jun/c-Fos, Transcription factors; Cyclin D1/E1, Cell cycle proteins; EGFR, Epidermal growth factor receptor; EMT, Epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition; ER α , Estrogen receptor alpha; ERK, Extracellular-signal-regulated kinase; FAK, Focal adhesion kinase; GSH, Glutathione; GPX1, Glutathione peroxidase 1; GSTP1/GSTO1, Glutathione S-transferases; HO-1, Heme oxygenase 1; IGFR, Insulin-like growth factor receptor; IL, Interleukin; MAPK, Mitogen-activated protein kinase; MEK, MAPK/ERK kinase; MMP, Matrix metalloproteinase; mTOR, Mammalian target of rapamycin; NF- κ B, Nuclear factor kappa B; NOX1, NADPH oxidase 1; PI3K, Phosphoinositide 3-kinase; ROS, Reactive oxygen species; SNAIL1, EMT-related transcription factor; SOD1, Superoxide dismutase 1; TNBC, Triple-negative breast cancer; TNF- α , Tumor necrosis factor alpha.

several indirect mechanisms. One of the primary drivers of Cd-induced oxidative stress is its interference with mitochondrial function, particularly by impairing the electron transport chain at Complex III, leading to structural impairment, electron leakage, and a progressive decline in mitochondrial membrane potential. Moreover, Cd fosters the accumulation of unstable semiquinones, which in turn promote excessive generation of reactive species, thereby exacerbating oxidative damage mitochondrial dysfunction (Hernández-Cruz et al., 2022). Cadmium exposure leads to aberrant NADPH oxidase (NOX) activation and overexpression, particularly of NOX1, resulting in uncontrolled superoxide anion (O₂^{•-}) production (Júnior et al., 2020). Additionally, Cd mobilizes redox-active metals, such as Fe. This metal is then displaced from intracellular storage proteins like ferritin and apoferritin, thereby leading to an increase in free Fe ions. The unbound Fe participates in Fenton and Haber-Weiss reactions, which catalyze the conversion of

hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) into highly reactive hydroxyl radicals ([•]OH), further amplifying oxidative damage (Cuypers et al., 2010). This oxidative insult is compounded by Cd's high affinity for sulfhydryl groups, leading to glutathione depletion and functional impairment of antioxidant enzymes, including superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and glutathione peroxidase (GPx), through catalytic topography perturbations, cofactor displacement, and transcriptional repression. Collectively, this enzyme impairment exacerbates oxidative damage and fosters a pro-tumorigenic environment (Lopez et al., 2006; Casalino et al., 2002; Montes et al., 2015). The resulting oxidative burden extends beyond disruptions in redox homeostasis, profoundly affecting nuclear and mitochondrial integrity. Excessive reactive species trigger oxidative DNA damage, leading to strand breaks and base modifications that can drive genomic instability. These mutations, coupled with impairments in DNA repair pathways, create a permissive environment for oncogenic

transformation (Genchi et al., 2020) (Fig. 3).

Cadmium exposure has been demonstrated to elicit a dose-dependent increase in the production of ROS in the MCF-7 human BC cell line, beginning at environmentally relevant concentrations of 0.1 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ and escalating to severe cytotoxicity at 1000 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ over 48 h. Significant cellular damage occurred at 10 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ and above, characterized by a marked decline in cell viability, nuclear condensation, chromatin fragmentation, and induction of apoptosis. Interestingly, co-treatment with N-acetylcysteine (NAC), a potent antioxidant and glutathione precursor, effectively counteracted Cd-induced cytotoxicity, reversing oxidative damage and protecting MCF-7 cells from apoptosis (Khojastehfar et al., 2015). Building on these findings, other research has demonstrated that Cd exposure exerts profound transcriptional modifications in genes responsible for oxidative stress regulation, inflammation, and cellular detoxification. Darwish et al. (2020) identified a dose-dependent downregulation of specific antioxidant defense genes, i.e., glutathione S-transferase omega 1 (GSTO1), NAD(P)H quinone dehydrogenase 1 (NQO1), superoxide dismutase 1 and 2 (SOD1, SOD2), and CAT, in MCF-7 cells following Cd treatment. In contrast, a compensatory upregulation of heme oxygenase-1 (HO-1), an Nrf2-regulated cytoprotective enzyme, was observed, likely as an adaptive response to counteract Cd-induced oxidative stress via the p38 MAPK/Nrf2 axis.

Simultaneously, Cd triggered inflammatory gene upregulation, including cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), and interleukins (IL-8, IL-10), highlighting the intersection between oxidative stress and inflammation-driven carcinogenesis. Interestingly, co-exposure to fat-soluble vitamins, particularly vitamin D, partially mitigated these effects by restoring MT-1 expression and xenobiotic transporter activity, suggesting that targeted dietary interventions could mitigate Cd-induced cytotoxicity. Expanding on these pathogenic mechanisms, recent findings have unveiled a novel pathway by which Cd triggers gasdermin E (GSDME)-dependent pyroptosis in BC cells (Tang et al., 2021). Pyroptosis, a highly inflammatory form of programmed cell death, is increasingly recognized as a determinant of tumor cell fate under oxidative stress conditions. In MDA-MB-231 cells Cd exposure (10–80 $\mu\text{mol/L}$) induced a dose-dependent reduction in viability, accompanied by S-phase cell cycle arrest and alterations in cyclin A1, cyclin D1, and cyclin-dependent kinase 2 (CDK2) expressions. The cytotoxic response was marked by lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) release, upregulation of BAX, and suppression of caspase-8, caspase-9, and caspase-3, indicative of a non-canonical cell death pathway. Cadmium activated the NLRP3 inflammasome, leading to the cleavage of caspase-1 and GSDME, with concomitant secretion of interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β) and interleukin-18 (IL-18), hallmark features of pyroptotic cell

Fig. 3. Schematic Representation of Cd-Induced Oxidative Stress and Mitochondrial Dysfunction in Breast Epithelial Cells. This illustration depicts the multifaceted pathways through which Cd^{2+} disrupts redox homeostasis, particularly focusing on mitochondrial dysfunction and downstream oxidative stress responses. Within the mitochondria, Cd impairs electron transport at Complex III, leading to semiquinone accumulation, electron leakage, and a reduction in mitochondrial membrane potential ($\Delta\Psi\text{m}$), culminating in bioenergetic failure. Excessive ROS production drives cytochrome c release, activation of caspases, mitochondrial outer membrane permeabilization (MOMP), and subsequent activation of the NLRP3 inflammasome, resulting in IL-1 β and IL-18 secretion. Cadmium also enhances NADPH oxidase (NOX) activity, further contributing to superoxide ($\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$) production. In parallel, Cd displaces essential cofactors such as Zn and selenium (Se) from antioxidant enzymes (e.g., SOD, CAT, GPx), weakening cellular antioxidant defenses. Elevated H_2O_2 levels undergo conversion via the Fenton reaction (Fe^{2+} -mediated), producing highly reactive hydroxyl radicals ($^{\bullet}\text{OH}$). These radical species initiate lipid peroxidation of membrane phospholipids, generating toxic aldehyde byproducts (e.g., 4-HNE, MDA) and compromising membrane integrity. In the nucleus, Cd-induced ROS leads to oxidative DNA damage, exemplified by the accumulation of 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine (8-OHdG), promoting genomic instability and pro-oncogenic transcriptional reprogramming. *Abbreviations:* 8-OHdG, 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine; 4-HNE, 4-hydroxy-2-nonenal; ATP, Adenosine triphosphate; CAT, Catalase; Cd^{2+} , Cadmium ion; Cyt c, Cytochrome c; $\Delta\Psi\text{m}$, Mitochondrial membrane potential; Fe^{2+} , Ferrous iron; GPx, Glutathione peroxidase; H_2O_2 , Hydrogen peroxide; IL, Interleukin; MDA, Malondialdehyde; MOMP, Mitochondrial outer membrane permeabilization; mtROS, Mitochondria-derived reactive oxygen species; NOX, NADPH oxidase; $\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$, Superoxide anion; ROS, Reactive oxygen species; SOD, Superoxide dismutase.

death. The pan-caspase inhibitor, z-VAD-fmk, effectively blocked both apoptosis and pyroptosis, highlighting the caspase-dependent nature of Cd-driven cell injury. Importantly, NAC co-treatment mitigated these effects by reducing reactive species' levels and also inflammasome activation, reinforcing the role of oxidative stress as a key upstream regulator. These findings underscore the complexity of Cd toxicity in BC cells, revealing pyroptosis as a previously underappreciated pathway that contributes to Cd's oncogenic potential.

In response to oxidative stress, cells attempt to mitigate proteotoxic damage by engaging heat shock proteins (HSPs), a conserved family of molecular chaperones involved in protein folding, stability, and stress adaptation. However, Cd exposure disrupts this finely tuned system, leading to selective HSP dysregulation in BC, thereby exacerbating cellular dysfunction. Studies on the MDA-MB-231 BC cell model have demonstrated a pronounced downregulation of HSPA5 (BiP), HSPD1 (HSP60), TRAP1, and HSP90AB1, all of which are integral to mitochondrial and endoplasmic reticulum (ER) proteostasis (summarized in [Luparello, 2021](#)). This suppression compromises protein homeostasis and heightens oxidative vulnerability, as HSPA5 depletion exacerbates ER stress, while the downregulation of HSPD1 and TRAP1 disrupts mitochondrial chaperoning, coinciding with increased respiratory activity and excessive generation of reactive species. In contrast, HSPB1 (Hsp27) is upregulated, likely reflecting an adaptive response to oxidative stress, yet remains insufficient to counteract the broader proteostatic imbalance. Notably, HSP60 mislocalization suggests a Cd-induced redistribution of mitochondrial chaperonins, further impairing protein quality control and contributing to mitochondrial dysfunction ([Cannino et al., 2008](#)). These perturbations, coupled with Cd-mediated disruptions in Ca signaling and apoptotic resistance, illustrate a broader oncogenic paradigm wherein oxidative stress, proteotoxicity, and metabolic reprogramming converge to promote tumor progression.

Cadmium exposure elicits a repertoire of adaptive cellular mechanisms, prominently involving the MTs that function in metal sequestration, redox regulation, and cytoprotection against heavy metal toxicity and oxidative damage. However, Cd's effects on MT expression are not uniform; rather, they are selectively modulated in a cell-type- and exposure-dependent manner. Comparative studies of tumor-derived breast epithelial cells and their immortalized non-malignant counterparts highlight these differential responses. In HB2 cells, Cd exposure primarily induces a protective response characterized by robust MT upregulation and enhanced detoxification pathways, mitigating oxidative and proteotoxic stress. In contrast, MDA-MB-231 BC cells exhibit a more complex response, wherein MT upregulation is accompanied by the activation of intracellular signaling cascades that predispose cells to an apoptotic-like cell fate. In this model, Cd exposure upregulates MT-1A, MT-1X, MT-1F, and MT-2A, while MT-1G is downregulated, indicating a nuanced transcriptional reprogramming rather than a generalized stress response ([Sirchia et al., 2008](#); [Alonso-Gonzalez et al., 2008](#)). This differential regulation is consistent with findings in other cellular systems, where MT-1A induction correlates with increased Cd resistance, whereas MT-1G depletion exacerbates oxidative vulnerability by impairing glutathione homeostasis and promoting lipid peroxidation ([Li et al., 2005](#); [Sun et al., 2016](#)). The predominant isoform in BC, MT-2A, has been linked to tumor progression and poor prognosis. Its upregulation correlates with increased proliferative capacity, apoptotic resistance, and heightened invasive potential, likely mediated through AP-1 and NF- κ B activation of matrix metalloproteinase-9 (MMP9) ([Jin et al., 2002](#); [Kim et al., 2011](#)). Moreover, MT overexpression in breast tumors was associated with hormone receptor negativity, elevated proliferative markers, and resistance to endocrine therapy, underscoring their roles in aggressive BC phenotypes. Beyond their role in detoxification, MTs influence intracellular metal homeostasis, particularly Cd accumulation and Zn displacement, with significant implications for tumor biology. One of the central guardians of genomic integrity, p53, is highly sensitive to Cd-induced

disruption, as Cd can displace Zn within its DNA-binding domain, impairing its tumor-suppressive functions. In this context, MT expression appears to be differentially regulated: p53-proficient BC cells exhibit stronger MT upregulation upon Cd exposure, coupled with heightened apoptotic susceptibility, whereas p53-deficient counterparts show attenuated MT induction and a blunted apoptotic response, potentially conferring a survival advantage and promoting tumor progression ([Fan et al., 2002](#)).

Beyond its impact on oxidative and proteotoxic stress, Cd disrupts genomic integrity by both inducing DNA lesions and compromising repair mechanisms, thereby increasing mutational burden and genomic instability. Studies in MCF-7 cells indicate that Cd disrupts base excision repair (BER) by selectively inhibiting key DNA glycosylases involved in oxidative and spontaneous base damage repair. The Cd-induced suppression of 8-oxoguanine glycosylase (hOGG1), responsible for excising 8-oxoguanine (8-oxoG), is linked to the protein's oxidation and then sequestration from the soluble fraction of cellular extracts. Notably, hOGG1 activity is partially restored upon Cd withdrawal, indicating a dynamic but reversible interference with BER. In contrast, the major apurinic/apyrimidinic endonuclease, APE1, remains unaffected, suggesting that Cd does not impair downstream BER processing ([Bravard et al., 2010](#)). In parallel with its inhibitory effects on DNA repair, Cd-driven genomic instability is compounded by extensive transcriptional alterations, modulating cell cycle progression, metal ion dynamics, and pro-oncogenic signaling pathways. Transcriptomic profiling of Cd-exposed MCF-7 cells has identified a distinct molecular signature associated with tumor progression. Cadmium upregulates genes implicated in cell cycle control, including CCNE1 and CCND1, encoding cyclins E1 and D1, respectively, which drive G1/S-phase transition and promote sustained proliferation. Simultaneously, Cd downregulates CDKN1A, encoding the cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor, p21/WAF1, thereby dampening cell cycle checkpoints and enhancing tumorigenic potential ([Liang et al., 2020](#); [Siewit et al., 2010](#)). This transcriptional pattern mirrors the dysregulation observed in aggressive BC subtypes, underscoring Cd's oncogenic influence on hormone-responsive cells. Beyond its impact on proliferative signaling, short-term Cd exposure in MCF-7 cells induces the upregulation of xenobiotic transporters MDR1 and MRP2, suggesting an adaptive mechanism to mitigate intracellular Cd accumulation ([Darwish et al., 2020](#)). Moreover, Cd perturbs epithelial integrity in MCF-7 cells by destabilizing E-cadherin/ β -catenin complexes, thereby promoting epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT). Through ubiquitin-mediated degradation, Cd reduces E-cadherin levels, weakening intercellular adhesion and facilitating the nuclear translocation of β -catenin. In the nucleus, β -catenin interacts with TCF-4, driving the upregulation of oncogenic targets, such as cyclin D1 and c-Jun. These transcriptional changes are more pronounced under chronic exposure, mirroring the progressive loss of epithelial traits seen in advanced BC phenotypes. This Cd-induced disruption of cell adhesion and transcriptional plasticity suggests a mechanistic link to increased invasiveness in hormone receptor-positive BC ([Ponce et al., 2015](#)). In contrast, Cd exposure in MDA-MB-231 TNBC cells elicits a distinct transcriptional response, characterized by profound dysregulation of apoptotic pathways, mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPKs), and key regulators of EMT. Cadmium directs MDA-MB-231 cells toward a cell death program with features of both apoptosis and programmed necrosis, as evidenced by BCL2 downregulation alongside DAPK1, WAF1, RIPK1, FOS, JUN, and caspase upregulation ([Luparello et al., 2021](#)). Concurrently, Cd exposure reinforces mesenchymal traits, driving a shift toward a more invasive phenotype. This is reflected in the upregulation of vimentin, a hallmark of mesenchymal identity, and the Cd-induced activation of Snail, a transcription factor central to EMT progression. Luciferase reporter assays confirm that Cd drives Snail expression at the promoter level, an effect abolished by actinomycin D, supporting a direct transcriptional regulatory mechanism. Functionally, Snail knockdown blocks Cd-induced cell migration, highlighting its role in driving the invasive potential of TNBC cells ([Wei et al., 2018](#)). Beyond

transcriptional regulation, Cd promotes pro-metastatic cytoskeletal reorganization, facilitating cell adhesion, migration, and invasion. In MDA-MB-231 cells, Cd exposure enhances integrin $\beta 1$ activation and downstream signaling via FAK, Src, and Rac1, pathways central to focal adhesion turnover and motility. Prolonged exposure further upregulates the integrins, $\alpha 5$ and $\beta 1$, and paxillin and vimentin, reinforcing cytoskeletal plasticity and cellular protrusions that drive invasive behavior. Importantly, Cd-mediated inhibition of GSK3 β activity enhances β -catenin stability and transcriptional activation via TCF/LEF, contributing to Cd-driven metastatic progression. These cellular changes correlate with increased secretion of the MMP2 and MMP9, further promoting extracellular matrix degradation and invasion (Wei and Shaikh, 2017). In addition to driving invasive and migratory behavior, Cd alters survival pathways in BC cells by modulating AEG1/MTDH, an oncogene implicated in tumor progression and tumor necrosis factor-related apoptosis-inducing ligand (TRAIL) resistance. In MDA-MB-231 TNBC cells, AEG1/MTDH depletion enhances susceptibility to TRAIL-induced apoptosis, likely through caspase-8 activation and Bcl-2 suppression via miR-16 regulation. Conversely, in MCF-7 hormone receptor-positive

cells, AEG1/MTDH overexpression confers TRAIL resistance by promoting Bcl-2 upregulation and inhibiting caspase activation. By antagonizing AEG1/MTDH expression, Cd paradoxically enhances TRAIL-mediated apoptotic susceptibility in TNBC, potentially shifting these highly aggressive cells toward a more vulnerable state (Zhang et al., 2013).

3. Association between cadmium and BC

3.1. Cadmium levels in clinical samples/materials of cases and controls

In this section, we included case-control, cross-sectional, and other types of studies that looked at potential differences in Cd levels in numerous human clinical samples (breast tissue, urine, whole blood, serum, and/or hair). Only studies that quantified Cd in clinical samples using atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS) or inductively coupled plasma (ICP)-based techniques were considered, to ensure the highest possible accuracy of our review analysis. General details about the literature search, study identification, and inclusion/exclusion process

Fig. 4. General details about the literature search, study identification, and inclusion/exclusion process for studies enrolled in this review.

for studies enrolled in this review are depicted in Fig. 4. Each study was critically appraised, to provide clearer guidelines for future research.

Breast tissue materials: Anđelković et al. (2021) provided information about Cd levels in healthy and malignant breast tissue materials. They included 55 cases and 41 women with benign breast changes. They noted about 3.5-fold higher levels of Cd in malignant breast tissues than in surrounding healthy breast tissues, which could indicate a different distribution and greater bioaccumulation of Cd in malignant tumor tissues. Also, a significant positive correlation between Cd levels in malignant and healthy breast tissues ($\rho = 0.502$) could be related to the development of breast cancer. They also found higher levels of Cd in malignant breast tissue materials from ER+ and PR+ cases than in their negative counterparts; these results could support a metalloestrogenic role of Cd in BC. Importantly, the authors found significantly higher Cd levels in malignant breast tissue materials of smokers than in non-smokers (their results were not presented numerically). In our opinion, the main limitation of this study was that cases and controls were not of the same age (61.2 ± 12.3 vs. 39.5 ± 10.8 years, respectively, $P < 0.01$) and had different BMI (25.7 vs. 22.9 kg/m², respectively, $P < 0.01$). Also, the authors did not state whether the cases were treated with medications or any other means before surgery. These limitations can skew results. Similarly, Jablonska et al. (2017) determined Cd in 42 malignant breast tumor tissues and 42 control tissues (at least 2 cm from the tumor border) collected from 42 women with primary BC (self-control study design). They found significantly higher Cd levels in malignant tumor tissues (median value = 85.9 ng/g) than in control tissues (median value = 66.5 ng/g). In addition, women who smoked had significantly higher Cd levels than non-smoking women, both in case tissues (270 ng/g vs. 126 ng/g, respectively) and control tissues (141 ng/g vs. 74 ng/g, respectively). No differences in tissue Cd levels were found according to menopausal status and BMI. Most importantly, the authors reported some differences in terms of tissue Cd levels and clinicopathological parameters/data. According to tumor type, they noted that cases with lobular BC had higher levels of Cd in tumor tissues than those with ductal or other types of breast carcinomas. They found that the highest levels of Cd were significantly associated with the smallest tumor sizes (T1) or low-grade tumors. According to receptor status, they found significantly higher Cd levels in PR+ cases compared to PR- cases, while Cd levels in ER+ cases were also numerically higher than in ER- cases, but the difference was not statistically significant. According to our opinion, although the number of participants included in the study was modest, this study indicates that malignant breast tissues can accumulate higher levels of Cd than the other/control part of the breast organ, and that there is evidence of the impact of Cd on the development and progression of BC. Romanowicz-Makowska et al. (2011) collected 67 ductal breast carcinoma samples from 67 women (52.8 ± 6.41 years, without distant metastases) who had undergone surgery and 16 control breast samples (tissue from the same patients excised from unaffected areas). All participants were from Lodz, Poland. They found significantly higher levels of Cd in breast carcinoma tissue (0.76 ± 0.38 µg/g dry weight) than in the control breast tissue (0.61 ± 0.24 µg/g dry weight). We stress that this difference could be swayed by the small number of controls, since the numerical values were practically the same. On the other hand, the authors did not find any significance in breast tissue Cd levels according to age, menopausal status, or histological grade of cancer, which could be explained by the previously mentioned small number of participants; for example, only 6 cases had stage III while the number of cases with stage I and stage II was 21 and 40, respectively. Strumylaite et al. (2011) compared Cd levels between malignant and healthy breast tissues and reported nearly 2.7-fold higher levels of Cd in the tissues of cases (median, 0.053 µg/g) than in control tissues (median, 0.020 µg/g) collected from the same patients ($n = 57$). ER+ cases had significantly higher levels of Cd in their breast tissues (median, 0.052 µg/g) than ER- cases (median, 0.035 µg/g). In contrast, Mohammadi et al. (2014) did not find significant differences in Cd levels in different BC tissues (tegmen, tumor

tissue, tumor adipose tissue, and tegmen adipose tissue) collected from 14 cases after mastectomy. However, the authors state that the absence of significant differences in Cd levels among the four tissue types was likely due to the close proximity of the sampling sites, which is also our opinion. In addition, the number of patients enrolled was too small to draw reliable conclusions. Antila et al. (1996) compared Cd levels in 43 malignant breast-adipose cancer tissues and 32 postmortem control tissues from participants who died accidentally or suddenly not from malignant disease and reported no significant differences between malignant breast tissues (20.4 ± 17.5 µg/g) and controls (31.7 ± 39.4 µg/g). In our opinion, a statistically significant difference was not detected since Cd was analyzed in tissue as close as possible to the malignant tumor, but not in the malignant tissue itself. Also, the control group was debatable; for example, a high standard deviation value in controls could indicate the presence of outliers. Interestingly, Ionescu et al. (2006) found significantly higher Cd levels in 20 BC biopsy materials compared with 8 control biopsy materials. In the future, more research should be conducted regarding Cd analysis on breast tissue materials after biopsy or surgery, particularly in terms of comparing malignantly altered and control/healthy tissue.

Whole blood and red blood cells: Peng et al. (2015) determined blood Cd levels in 186 cases (49.3 ± 10.5 years) and 139 controls (48.8 ± 15.0 years) from Chaoshan, southeast China. They found significantly higher Cd blood levels in cases (median, 2.28 µg/L) than in controls (median, 1.77 µg/L). The authors then used 3 µg/L as the cutoff value for blood Cd level, divided them into high and low Cd groups, and calculated the proportions between cases and controls. The proportion of blood Cd levels above 3 µg/L was nearly 2.35-fold higher in cases compared to controls after adjusting for age. Cases older than 50 years had significantly higher blood Cd levels than cases younger than 50 years, which could indicate accumulation of Cd with age. Both the high BMI group (≥ 23.9 kg/m²) and the low BMI group (< 18.5 kg/m²) had significantly higher blood Cd levels than the optimal BMI group, indicating the altered levels of Cd with different BMI profiles. In addition, blood Cd levels were significantly associated with the clinical stage; cases in advanced clinical stages had significantly higher blood Cd levels than those in lower clinical stages. They found the same for advanced T and M, but not for the N groups; for example, cases with metastases (M1) had significantly higher blood Cd levels than cases without metastases (M0). According to the expression of ER, PR, and Cerb-B2 (or Her 2/neu – human epidermal growth factor receptor), they found no association between ER or PR status with blood Cd levels, but they reported that cases with positive Cerb-B2 had higher blood Cd levels than cases with negative Cerb-B2. Since the authors found significantly higher levels of Cd in the blood in advanced stages of the disease, their results could indicate the role of Cd in promoting the development of BC. Saleh et al. (2011) included 50 newly diagnosed stages I cases (47.2 ± 11.8 years) and 150 healthy controls (46.9 ± 12.5) from Kuwait. They found significantly higher blood Cd levels in cases (5.87 ± 1.53 µg/L) than in controls (3.81 ± 1.90 µg/L). Interestingly, they reported that high blood Cd levels were significantly associated with micronucleus formation in lymphocytes. Anđelković et al. (2021) reported no significant differences between cases ($n = 55$) and controls (women with benign breast changes) ($n = 41$) for blood Cd levels (the authors did not show results numerically). Gaudet et al. (2019) prospectively aimed to study the association between Cd levels in red blood cells and BC risk in three case-control studies (1435 cases and 1433 controls). Overall, they found no significant differences to support a link between Cd levels in red blood cells and BC risk. We would like to highlight several shortcomings of this study, including the different numbers and different ages of the cases and controls in the three studies, the differences in the age of the women between the three studies, and the different time intervals (in years) between the three studies when blood was collected for analysis. As is known, whole blood or red blood cells reflect Cd status over a narrow time period (Stojavljević and Rovčanin, 2021). In our opinion, the finding of Gaudet et al. (2019), that women with Cd levels of 2 µg/L

or higher had a lower risk of BC than women with the lowest levels of Cd in their red blood cells, should be questioned.

Serum and urine: [Matin et al. \(2024\)](#) examined serum and urine Cd levels in 40 newly diagnosed cases and 30 age-matched healthy controls, with ER- and HER-2 status, from Iran. They found significantly higher serum Cd levels in cases ($0.57 \pm 0.10 \mu\text{g/L}$) than in controls ($0.29 \pm 0.06 \mu\text{g/L}$), as well as in urine of cases ($3.90 \pm 2.80 \mu\text{g/g}$) than in controls ($1.36 \pm 0.60 \mu\text{g/g}$). Accordingly, they observed that for every 1 $\mu\text{g/g}$ increase in Cd levels in urine, the chances of developing BC increased about 2-fold. A significant difference was found for urine Cd levels among lower grade cases (I + II) ($3.99 \pm 2.65 \mu\text{g/g}$) than among those with higher grade (III + IV) ($1.64 \pm 0.75 \mu\text{g/g}$). Also, significantly higher serum and urine Cd levels were found for cases based on ER status (ER+ vs. ER-) and PR status (PR+ vs. PR-), respectively, while no significant differences were found based on HER2 (HER2+ vs. HER2-) status. Although this study provides very useful information, it had a small sample number of individuals, while cases and controls differed significantly in BMI (29.1 ± 5.20 vs. $25.8 \pm 3.70 \text{ kg/m}^2$, respectively), which could have influenced the results. [Burton et al. \(2016\)](#) found no significant differences in urine Cd levels between 47 cases (median, $0.67 \mu\text{g/L}$) and 84 controls with benign conditions (median, $0.61 \mu\text{g/L}$) from Springfield, US. Although the authors controlled the analytical phase (ICP-MS quantification of Cd in collision/helium mode), the preanalytical phase in that study is more controversial. For example, the uneven number of participants, failure to include healthy volunteers, and the wide age range of cases and controls (33–84 years) can skew the results. [Men et al. \(2020\)](#) reported about 2-fold significantly higher urine Cd levels in Chinese cases ($n = 106$) than in controls ($n = 38$). As with previous studies, the uneven number of cases and controls could lead to errors. [Strumylaite et al. \(2011\)](#) found about 2-fold significantly higher creatinine-adjusted urine Cd levels in cases ($0.053 \mu\text{g/g}$) than in controls ($0.02 \mu\text{g/g}$). A limitation of this study was mentioned previously (see above).

Keratin material/hair: Only one study on these matrices has been conducted to date. [Benderli Cihan et al. \(2011\)](#) determined numerous elements in hair collected from 52 patients with stage III BC (50 ± 9 years) and 52 healthy controls (47 ± 10 years) from Turkey. They found significantly higher levels of Cd in the hair of cases ($0.44 \pm 0.49 \mu\text{g/g}$) than in controls ($0.18 \pm 0.21 \mu\text{g/g}$). According to our opinion, the higher standard deviation value than the mean for both cases and controls indicates the existence of outliers or nonparametric distribution of the data. Other shortcomings were directly related to the potential impact of medications and surgical interventions, as the study included cases with advanced stages of BC.

A meta-analysis by [Liu et al. \(2022\)](#) included eight case-control studies and reported significantly higher Cd levels in serum/plasma and hair of cases than in controls. They also reported that serum/plasma Cd levels were significantly higher in cases from Asia (China, Iraq, and Kuwait) than in controls, while differences in Cd levels (cases vs. controls) were only significant for the hair of the European population analyzed. However, no meta-analyses of the other clinical matrices we have discussed herein have been conducted, so this needs to be done as soon as possible.

In summary, according to the literature data, it can be concluded that Cd levels in clinical matrices collected from BC patients are notably higher than those in controls. Although some authors of the aforementioned studies have claimed causality between higher Cd levels in clinical matrices and BC, it is not that simple. This is actually reverse causality, as the clinical matrices were collected after the diagnosis of BC. Any type of medical intervention (drugs therapy, surgery, etc.) or the disease itself can alter levels of trace metals, including Cd, or alter the metabolism of essential trace elements (Zn, Cu, Se and other), which alters Cd levels in the body (antagonistic interactions) ([Stojšavljević et al., 2023](#)).

Cadmium levels in urine are a subject of scientific debate. One group of researchers advocates that Cd is a cumulative toxin and that urine

reflects long-term Cd retention in the body (over the years) ([Vacchi-Suzzi et al., 2016](#)). Another group of researchers argues that urine does not accurately reflect Cd accumulation in the kidneys as a result of long-term exposure to low levels, meaning that Cd in urine could reflect recent exposure rather than cumulative exposure ([Chaumont et al., 2012](#), [Chaumont et al., 2013](#)). In addition, some studies show that the association between kidney Cd levels and urine Cd levels can be weaker in older than in younger adults, in part since Cd levels in both clinical matrices reach a plateau around age 50 ([Akerstrom et al., 2013](#); [Barregard et al., 2010](#)). These discrepancies should be resolved in the future.

3.2. Breast cancer density and Cd levels

Regarding BC density and urine/blood Cd levels, only three studies have been reported so far. In a cross-sectional study, [Adams et al. \(2011\)](#) examined the potential association between mammographic density (MD, a suitable marker/predictor of BC risk) and creatinine-normalized urine Cd levels in 190 women aged 40–45 years from Washington, US. The determined urine Cd levels normalized by creatinine ranged from 0.06 to $1.56 \mu\text{g/g}$. They found that the mean percent of MD (MD%) among women in the highest tertile was 4.60 % higher than that of women in the lowest Cd tertile. They also noted that each 2-fold increase in urine Cd levels was related to a higher risk of MD%. Most importantly, these associations were stronger in women who had never given birth and in women who were current or former smokers compared to those who had given birth and had never smoked. The authors concluded that higher urine Cd levels were associated with increased MD in premenopausal women. In our opinion, since MD is one of the more reliable indicators for BC, their study provides valuable information about the impact of Cd on malignant breast tumors. Still, the question arises: does the risk of MD% increase with increasing levels of Cd in urine in postmenopausal women? This reasonable question should be answered by future studies. However, six years later in a letter to the editor, [Adams et al. \(2017\)](#) reported no significant association between MD% and urine Cd levels for 725 women aged 40–65 years, which we find interesting since the median urine Cd level was $0.27 \mu\text{g/g}$ -creatinine, which is higher than in their previous study. In addition, [Peplowska et al. \(2020\)](#) did not find a significant association between urine Cd levels and breast density in middle-aged Polish women (40–60 years) who underwent screening mammography. However, they reported a significant association between urine Cd levels and fibroglandular tissue volume in a group of nulliparous women.

Overall, 2 out of 3 studies do not support an association between BC density and Cd levels in clinical materials. Given that BC density is an extremely suitable marker for BC diagnosis, we suggest that authors of future studies shed light on these contradictory findings.

3.3. Cadmium levels and sex hormones in BC

As mentioned earlier, estrogen is one of the risk factors for BC ([Al-Shami et al., 2023](#)). Testosterone is an androgen secreted by both the adrenal glands and the ovaries in women. Although ovarian testosterone production decreases slightly after menopause, its levels remain relatively constant ([Burger, 2002](#)). Details on the impact of reproductive hormones on BC risk independent of Cd exposure are not the primary focus of this review and can be found elsewhere ([Key et al., 2002, 2011](#); [Tin Tin et al., 2021](#)).

Several studies have examined the association between Cd levels and sex hormone levels in clinical materials collected from BC patients. [Ali et al. \(2014\)](#) conducted a cross-sectional study and found a significant association between blood Cd levels and serum testosterone levels, and significant negative associations between blood and urine Cd levels and serum estradiol levels in 438 postmenopausal Swedish women aged 50–59 years. They concluded that Cd could affect the levels of these two hormones (disrupting the balance of estrogen and androgen), increasing

the risk of breast tumors. Nagata et al. (2013) found a significant positive association between urine Cd levels and serum testosterone levels. Anđelković et al. (2021) conducted a case-control study and found positive correlations between Cd levels in malignant breast tissues (n = 55) and serum levels of follicle stimulating hormone (FSH) and luteinizing hormone (LH), and negative correlations with serum estradiol levels and the free estradiol index (FEI). They also found a positive correlation between Cd levels in healthy breast tissues (n = 41) with LH levels. No significant correlations were found for the other hormones analyzed, testosterone and sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG), in the case or control group. Buha Djordjevic et al. (2021) reported a dose-response relationship between Cd levels in breast tissues (tumorous and healthy surrounding tissues) and serum estradiol levels (lower estradiol levels could be a consequence of higher Cd levels).

Further research is urgently needed to establish a clearer link between Cd and reproductive hormones and thereby identify or rule out a biomarker from blood or urine that would have preventive, diagnostic, or prognostic significance.

4. Association between Cd and BC risk

4.1. Association between dietary Cd intake and BC risk without measuring Cd levels in clinical matrices

Intake of Cd through food is the main route of entry of this element into the body (Charkiewicz et al., 2023). Studies addressing this topic have primarily considered completing questionnaires with data to assess daily Cd intake (food frequency questionnaire, FFQ) from baseline to multi-year cohort follow-up (prospective study design). The authors designed their studies to combine responses from a FFQ with analytical data on Cd levels in food from a national market-basket survey or other

sources. These studies include a large number of participants from different countries around the world, which gives us the opportunity to conduct a comprehensive and critical analysis of these works.

Details of the included studies are given in Fig. 4 and Table 2. Here we have provided an overview of the most important findings. Adams et al., 2011; Adams et al., 2012 enrolled 1026 postmenopausal women (aged 50–79) with invasive BC from the Puget Sound region of Washington State, US. The estimated daily dietary intake of Cd was $10.9 \pm 4.90 \mu\text{g}$. They found no significant association between dietary Cd and the risk of BC, even after adjusting for smoking habits, total vegetable consumption, mineral use (intake of Zn, Fe, or Ca from supplement or dietary sources), and BC risk factors (parity, BMI, postmenopausal hormone replacement therapy, and ER-status of malignant breast tumors). In a subsequent study, Adams et al. (2014) reported virtually the same results for 6658 women with invasive BC at an average follow-up of 10.5 years. Eriksen et al. (2014) found no significant association between dietary Cd intake and BC risk in 1390 postmenopausal Danish women. The estimated daily dietary Cd intake was $14 \mu\text{g}$, with no significant difference in dietary Cd intake between cases and cohort. They also found no significant association in subgroup analyses between ER status (ER+ vs. ER-), PR status (PR+ vs. PR-), or for the two most common histological types (ductal and lobular), although a trend toward a positive association with dietary Cd intake was recorded for lobular breast carcinoma. They also noted that neither Zn nor Fe altered the relationship between Cd intake and BC risk. Itoh et al. (2014) included 405 cases and 405 controls from Japan, a population with a relatively high dietary intake of Cd. They found no significant association between dietary Cd intake and overall BC risk, or among strata of menopausal status and smoking. However, in postmenopausal women, the authors found a positive association between dietary Cd intake and ER+ /PR- cases. They reported a continuous increase in the risk of

Table 2

Details of the included studies that looked at the association of dietary Cd intake with BC risk.

Ref.	Country	Study design	Recruitment period	Monitoring duration	Type of Population	Age	Cases/sample size	Dietary Cd intake ($\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$)	Results HR/RR (95 % CI)*	Yes/No association between biological materials and BC risk
Adams et al., (2012)	United States	Cohort	2000–2002	7.5 years (from 2009)	Postmenopausal	50–76	899/26,801	(mean \pm SD) Q1 = 5.80 ± 1.20 Q2 = 8.8 ± 0.70 Q3 = 11.6 ± 0.90 Q4 = 17.4 ± 4.30	HR = 1.00 (0.72–1.41)	No
Adams et al., (2014)	United States	Cohort	1993–1998	10.5 years (from 2009)	Postmenopausal	50–79	6658/150,889	(quintile) Q1 = < 7.10 Q2 = 7.10–9.24 Q3 = 9.24–11.4 Q4 = 11.4–14.2 Q5 = > 14.2	HR = 0.90 (0.81–1.00)	Yes
Eriksen et al., (2014)	Denmark	Cohort	1993–1997	13 years (from 2010)	Postmenopausal	50–65	1390/23,815	(tertiles) T1 = < 11.9 T2 = 11.9–15.3 T3 = > 15.3	RR = 0.97 (0.85–1.11)	No
Julin et al., (2012)	Sweden	Prospective cohort study	1987–1990	12.2 years (from 2008)	Postmenopausal	42–76	2112/55,987	(quintile) Q1 = < 13 Q2 = 13–16 Q3 = > 16	RR = 1.21 (1.07–1.36)	Yes
Griioni et al. (2019)	Italy	Prospective cohort study	1987–1992	22.1 years (from 2012)	Pre- and postmenopausal	34–70	481/8924	(quintile) Q1 = 0.45–6.72 Q2 = 6.73–7.40 Q3 = 7.41–8.02 Q4 = 8.03–8.81 Q5 = 8.82–16.10	HR = 1.54 (1.06–2.22)	Yes
Sawada et al., 2012	Japan	Cohort	1990–1993	9 years (from 2006)	Pre- and postmenopausal	45–74	402/48,351	(tertiles) T1 = 18.1 T2 = 22.9 T3 = 27.1 T4 = 33.9	HR = 0.96 (0.81–1.15)	No

* Dietary Cd intake and risk of BC (highest to lowest quartile).

postmenopausal ER+ breast tumor with increasing Cd levels for every 1.0 µg/day increases in Cd intake. In contrast, no differences were found for ER- cases or for PR+ or PR- breast tumors. They also found that in the low BMI group, Cd intake was negatively associated with BC risk, while this association was not significant in the high BMI group. The reported daily Cd intake for Japan in their study (26.4 µg/day) is similar to previously reported data for the same country (25.5 µg/day) (Watanabe et al., 2000). A meta-analysis that included six studies by Wu et al. (2015) reported no significant association between dietary Cd and BC risk. Also, a meta-analysis by Van Maele-Fabry et al. (2016) found no significantly increased risk of BC in postmenopausal women associated with dietary Cd intake (6 studies between 2012 and 2014). The authors noted inconsistency between studies regarding geographic location, BMI, HRT use, ER status, PR, smoking status, and Zn and Fe absorption, which is also our opinion.

On the other hand, two studies reported positive association between dietary Cd intake and BC risk. Grioni et al. conducted a 22-year prospective study in which they included 451 Italian cases. The mean estimated daily intake of Cd was 7.8 ± 1.4 µg. They found that increasing dietary Cd intake was significantly associated with an increased risk of BC. Although the authors failed to find a significant risk of BC with dietary Cd intake depending on ER (ER+ vs. ER-), PR (PR+ vs. PR-), or HER2 (HER2+ vs. HER2-) status, they observed that Cd intake was significantly associated with an increased risk of ER+ and PR+ BC. The associations were stronger for the fully adjusted model, including adjustment for dietary Fe, Ca, and Zn. The authors suggested that the increased risk of BC, especially in premenopausal women, was partly due to higher Cd absorption due to mild chronic Fe deficiency, and perhaps also Zn and Ca deficiencies. The authors also found a significant association for HER2-negative BC. Although this study was well designed, we stress that the number of cases was insufficient, depending on BC receptor status, for a period of 22 years. Other shortcomings were similar to those in previously analyzed studies. Julin et al. (2012) included 2112 Swedish postmenopausal cases with invasive BC during a mean follow-up period of 12.2 years to examine the potential association between dietary Cd intake and the risk of overall BC and subtype, depending on ER status (1626 ER+ and 290 ER-). The mean estimated daily intake of Cd was 15 ± 3.2 µg. They found that dietary Cd intake was positively associated with overall BC, even after adjusting for whole grains, vegetables, and other BC risk factors. A significant positive association with dietary Cd intake was also found for ER+ breast tumors, but not for ER- breast tumors.

Overall, we can conclude that studies looking at dietary Cd and BC risk do not indicate a strong association between the two. We would like to highlight several shortcomings in the design of the aforementioned studies. First, information on women's exposure to Cd from FFQ is debatable since dietary Cd intake reflects women's recent exposure to Cd, which can vary depending on the timing of exposure, season, food processing, etc.; consequently, these studies are subject to multiple sources of errors. Second, the authors did not quantify Cd in food (which is often not even from the same locale in which the research is conducted), but rather relied on general data from relevant monitoring agencies (e.g., the US FDA). Third, intake measures from FFQ do not reflect the actual absorbed dose of Cd and other micronutrients; for example, women with reduced blood ferritin levels and altered Fe metabolism have impaired Cd absorption (Rolić et al., 2025). Fourth, women can be exposed to Cd from other sources (in the workplace, through polluted air, through potable water sourced from nearby industrial plants, etc.). All of these factors should be taken into account to most reliably assess the association between dietary Cd and BC risk. Special attention should be paid to smokers, vegans and vegetarians, as well as women who eat a balanced diet but are deficient in Ca, Fe, and/or Zn. Although it is difficult to control for all of these factors, we urge authors of future studies to consider these suggestions and minimize errors as much as possible.

4.2. Association between dietary Cd intake and urinary or blood Cd levels with BC risk

Details of the included studies are given in Fig. 4 and Table 3. Here we have provided an overview of the most important findings. Adams et al. (2016) conducted a case-cohort study and examined the association between urine Cd levels and BC risk. Over an average follow-up period of 13.2 years, they enrolled 508 postmenopausal cases with invasive BC and 1050 postmenopausal cohort women. The authors found no significant association between creatinine-normalized urine Cd levels and invasive BC risk in either the total number of participants or subgroups (smoking habits, BMI, hormone therapy, or ER/PR status). Eriksen et al. (2016) conducted a prospective case-cohort study to examine potential connections between Cd levels in urine and the risk of BC in postmenopausal Danish women (50–64 years). They enrolled 900 BC patients and 898 participants (cohort). They found no significant association between urine Cd levels and BC risk at least four years before the date of BC diagnosis overall, or between subgroups (ER and PG status and histology). Interestingly, they reported that higher urine Cd levels were associated with a higher risk of BC among current smokers (relative to non-smokers) and former HRT users (relative to those who had never used HRT). O'Brien et al. (2020) noted no significant association between Cd levels in toenails and young-onset BC risk in US women. Wei et al. (2015) included 240 invasive BC cases and 246 age-matched controls from Guangzhou, China. They found that there was only a 16 % increased BC risk for each 1 µg/g increase in urine Cd. However, they pointed out that the association of urine Cd with BC risk was modified by urine Se levels, especially in postmenopausal women. Nagata et al. (2013) included 153 women with newly diagnosed BC and 431 controls matched to the cases by age, menopausal status, and urine sampling period. All individuals were from Gifu, Japan. They found a positive association between urine Cd levels and BC risk; a trend toward higher BC risk was significantly associated with each 1.0 µg/g increase in urine Cd levels. Additional adjustment for parity, rice intake, dietary Ca, Zn, Cu, and Fe intake, HRT, and smoking habits did not significantly change the results. Strumylaite et al. (2014) included 585 newly diagnosed cases and 1170 controls from Lithuania. They found a significant association between urine Cd levels and BC risk; a 1.6-fold increase in BC risk in women with urine Cd ≥ 0.241 µg/g creatinine than in participants with urine Cd levels < 0.147 µg/g creatinine after adjusting for age. Adjusting for other confounding factors (smoking, BMI, parity, hormone therapy during menopause, and family history of BC) did not change the association of Cd with BC risk ($P < 0.01$). Additionally, they found that ER+ cases had about a 2-fold higher risk of BC after adjustment for confounding factors, while ER- cases did not have a statistically significantly different BC risk than the control group. Regarding HER2 status, a significant association was found between urine Cd levels and HER2-, but not with HER2+ after adjustment for confounding factors. Accordingly, the authors reported a statistically higher risk of BC in ER+ /HER2- cases after adjusting for confounding factors, while ER- /HER2-, ER- /HER2+, and ER+ /HER2+ cases did not reach statistical significance. Five years later, Strumylaite et al. (2019) examined the association of urine Cd levels with histological and tumor receptor subtype of BC. They enrolled 509 cases with invasive BC (ductal and lobular carcinoma) and 1170 controls. Similar to their previous study, they found an association between urine Cd levels and invasive ductal ER+, PR+, ER+ /PR+, HER2-, and ER+ /PR+ /HER2-, as well as HER2- (but not HER2+) breast carcinoma. Due to the different tumor receptor status in ductal and lobular carcinomas, a strongest positive association with urine Cd levels was found for ER+ /PR+ /HER2- ductal breast carcinoma. However, they did not find any association between urine Cd and carcinomas with different tumor histology. McElroy et al. (2006) enrolled 246 cases and 254 age-matched control women from Wisconsin, US. They reported that women in the highest Cd quartile (creatinine-corrected urine Cd levels ≥ 0.58 µg/g) had more than twice the risk of BC than women in

Table 3
Association between dietary Cd intake and urine or blood cadmium levels with BC risk.

Ref.	Biological material	Study design	Country	Recruitment period	Monitoring duration	Type of Population	Age	Cases/ sample size	Cadmium level ($\mu\text{g/g}$ - creatinine)	Measures of central tendency and dispersion	Yes/No association between biological materials and BC risk
Adams et al., (2016)	Urine	Case-cohort	United States	1993–1998	13.2 years (from 2010)	Postmenopausal	50–79	508/ 1050	Mean \pm SD: 0.63 0.50, median (IQR): 0.51 (0.33–0.77)	highest (>0.75) vs. lowest (<0.33) quartile ($\mu\text{g/g}$ cr)	No
Eriksen et al. (2016)	Urine	Cohort	Denmark	1993–1997	> 13 years (from 2011)	Postmenopausal	50–65	898/ 23,379	Median IQR: 0.54 (0.14–1.94)	highest (0.42–5.41) vs. lowest (<0.16) tertile (ng/ mL)	No
Wei et al., (2015)	Urine	Case-Control	China	2009–2010	-	Premenopausal Postmenopausal Overall	Cases: 50.1 \pm 11.7 Controls: 51.6 \pm 12.0 Cases: 53.1 \pm 12.1 Controls: 50.7 \pm 10.7	240/ 486	(geometric mean) Cases: 1.93 Controls: 1.80 median (IQR) Cases: 2.72 (2.49–2.97) Controls: 2.09 (1.98–2.19)	highest (>2.36) vs. lowest (1.59) tertile ($\mu\text{g/g}$ cr)	No
Nagata et al., (2013)	Urine	Case-Control	Japan	2000–2002	NR	Overall		153/ 584	Median (IQR) Cases: 2.72 (2.49–2.97) Controls: 2.09 (1.98–2.19)	highest (>2.620) vs. lowest (1.674) tertile ($\mu\text{g/g}$ cr)	Yes
García-Esquinas et al. (2014)	Urine	Prospective cohort study	United States	1989–1991	17.2 years (from 2008) mortality	Pre- and postmenopausal	45–74	25/ 2254	median (IQR): 0.93 (0.61–1.46)	highest (1.98) vs. lowest (0.51) percentile ($\mu\text{g/g}$ cr)	No
Lin et al., (2013)	Urine	Prospective cohort study	United States	1988–1994	12.4 years (from 2007) mortality	All postmenopausal	\geq 50	26/ 2730	Median (IQR): 0.77 (0.47–1.27)	highest (1.65) vs. lowest (1.00) percentile ($\mu\text{g/g}$ cr)	No
Andersson et al., (2021)	Blood	Case-Control	Sweden	1991–1996	until December 31, 2014	Overall	Cases: 56.2 (44.7–73.5) Controls: 56.2 (44–73) Heterogeneous	1274/ 3846	(mean) Cases: 0.51 $\mu\text{g/L}$ Controls: 0.46 $\mu\text{g/L}$ N.P.	highest (1.20–4.99) vs. lowest (0.04–0.41) ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Yes
Gaudet et al., (2019)	Blood	Case-Control	United States, Italy, Sweden	Varies depending on country	N.R.	Overall		1435/ 2868	N.P.	highest (>2.00) vs. lowest (0–0.49) quintile ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	No
Strumylaite et al., (2019)	Urine	Case-Control	Lithuania	2007–2011	N.R.	Postmenopausal	Cases: 58.1 \pm 12.3 Controls: 57.4 \pm 12.5	509/ 1679	Cases: 0.29 (0.18–0.43) Controls: 0.24 (0.15–0.40)	highest (>0.33) vs. lowest (<0.18) tertile	Yes
Gallagher et al., (2010)	Urine	Case-control of two studies (Long Island + NHANES)	United States	ET	ET	Overall	ET	192/ 3174	ET	highest (\geq 0.60) vs. lowest (<0.22) quartile	Yes
McElroy et al., (2006)	Urine	Case-control	United States	2004–2005	N.R.	Overall	20–69	246/ 500	N.P.	highest (\geq 0.58) vs. lower (<0.26) quartile	Yes

NR = not relevant; NP = not presented; ET = explanation in the text.

the lowest Cd quartile ($< 0.26 \mu\text{g/g}$). Gallagher et al. (2010) compared urine Cd levels between women living on Long Island (LI) New York (100 cases and 98 controls, mean age for cases and controls was 63 ± 9 and 59 ± 11 , respectively) with women enrolled in the US National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) 1999–2008 study (92 cases and 2884 controls, mean age for cases and controls was 67 ± 13 and 54 ± 16 , respectively). They chose LI because of its higher incidence of BC. They found that the increased risk of BC with increasing urine Cd levels was significant for LI and NHANES women independent of tobacco use. They summarized that urine Cd $> 0.60 \mu\text{g/creatinine}$ was associated with an increased risk of BC. In our opinion, the main limitations of this study relate to differences in study design (case-control design for LI women and cross-sectional design for NHANES women), differences in years since BC diagnosis (5–12 years for LI women and 7 years for NHANES women) and demographics (e.g., age differences between controls and cases, different tobacco consumption between groups, different residence of LI women compared to NHANES women, different number of cases and controls in NHANES study, etc.).

Cho et al. (2013) conducted a meta-analysis using eight studies, two of which were case-control studies and six were cohort studies. They found no significant differences overall between dietary Cd intake and BC risk, but they did find a significant positive association between dietary Cd intake and BC risk (highest dietary Cd group vs. lowest dietary Cd group) only among studies conducted in Western countries. However, the authors combined these eight studies that examined Cd levels in breast, endometrial, and/or ovarian cancer and presented them as one meta-analysis, not giving us as clear a picture of the association of Cd with BC risk alone (only two case-control and two cohort studies addressed the association between dietary Cd and BC risk). A meta-analysis by Rahim et al. (2013) included 13 studies (978 cases and 1279 controls). They found a significantly higher BC risk in Asians and Caucasians with high blood Cd levels, in favor of Asians over Caucasians, compared with controls. As with a previously mentioned meta-analysis, the authors combined Cd levels for different clinical matrices (urine, whole blood, and breast tissue) and drew conclusions. These types of data meta-processing lead to great heterogeneity, errors and, consequently, inaccuracy. Larsson et al. (2015) enrolled two cohort studies, five case-control studies, and one cross-sectional study to examine the association between urine Cd levels and BC risk during the time period 2006–2015. They reported that urine Cd was positively associated with BC in case-control and cross-sectional studies, while no association were found in cohort studies. According to the authors, each $0.5\text{-}\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine increase in urine Cd levels was associated with a 66 % increased risk of BC, indicating that high Cd exposure could be a risk factor for BC. Lin et al. (2016) included six studies on dietary Cd intake and five studies on urine Cd levels. They found no significant association between dietary Cd intake and BC risk. After subgroup analysis, no significant associations were obtained according to ER status (ER+ vs. ER-), menopausal status (pre- or postmenopausal), or country of BC patients. However, they found a significant association between urine Cd levels and BC risk; an increase in urine Cd of $1 \mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine was associated with a nearly one-fold increase in BC. Jouybari et al. (2018) conducted a meta-analysis using 11 studies and showed a significant association between BC risk and Cd levels in three different clinical matrices (plasma, breast tissue, and keratin tissue – hair and nails). When they excluded two studies that looked at plasma Cd levels and two studies that looked at Cd levels in breast tissue, they noted the association between BC risk and Cd levels in keratin tissues was still statistically relevant. Nonetheless, they did not find significant differences in Cd levels between healthy controls and cases within either the plasma or the breast tissue subgroups. As with the previously mentioned meta-analyses, this one also showed significant heterogeneity. Filippini et al. (2020) conducted a meta-analysis using 10 studies, 6 of which were based on dietary Cd intake and 4 on urine Cd levels. They found no link between dietary or urine Cd levels and BC risk in postmenopausal women. However, the authors pointed out that data on age, smoking

habits, and hormone receptor status were limited in conducting reliable meta-subgroup analyses, which is also our opinion. A meta-analysis by Florez-Garcia et al. (2023) showed that higher levels of Cd were associated with a 13 % higher risk of developing BC, but they did not show a significant association between dietary Cd levels, airborne Cd, or biomarkers (in urine and blood) with BC risk. For Cd levels in urine and blood, they showed a 37 % increased risk of developing BC, but this was not statistically significant. In our opinion, the reason why the authors concluded that BC risk increases with increasing Cd levels is that they combined 17 studies in an overall meta-analysis that looked at Cd levels in different matrices (air, food, urine, blood) as a single matrix. Accordingly, the authors reported a large heterogeneity between studies ($I^2 = 77\%$). Also, the authors combined Cd levels for two different clinical matrices (urine and blood) as a single matrix, which is not a reliable approach for assessing the impact of Cd on any human neoplasm, including BC. Consequently, they reported an $I^2 = 84\%$, indicating very high heterogeneity and biases. We observed less heterogeneity in those subgroups that were properly incorporated. Overall, in our opinion, the results of this meta-analysis should be interpreted with caution.

4.3. Airborne Cd and the risk of BC

Advanced industrialization in the last few decades has contributed to the uncontrolled release of metals, including Cd, into the environment (Briffa et al., 2020). For example, Wan et al. (2019) demonstrated that atmospheric metal pollution before 1950 was negligible in mainland China, increased slightly during 1950–1980, while since 1980, air pollution has increased sharply. According to the IARC and a large number of epidemiological studies, airborne particulates and contaminants are strongly associated with a higher incidence of respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, as well as cancer in people who have been exposed to contaminated air for a long time. It is estimated that inhaled Cd has a greater capacity to remain in the body than ingested Cd (Amadou et al., 2020). Women's exposure to Cd through air is one of the main inhalation sources of intake into the body (Genchi et al., 2020).

Several population studies have examined the association between airborne Cd levels and risk of BC. Amadou et al. (2010) enrolled 4059 cases (primary invasive BC) and 4059 matched controls from France. They found no significant association between long-term airborne exposure to Cd and BC risk in both premenopausal and postmenopausal cases. Yet, they reported lower risks (negative associations) for ER- and ER-/PR- breast tumors in postmenopausal women. Two years later, Amadou et al. (2021) included 4401 cases (predominantly with stages I and II) and 4401 matched controls and reported no significant association between cumulative exposure to airborne Cd and BC stage or grade of differentiation, but found a significant positive association between airborne Cd and the risk of invasive tubular breast carcinoma. However, they did not find a significant association of airborne Cd exposure and invasive lobular carcinoma, invasive ductal carcinoma, or combined breast carcinomas. Kresovich et al. (2019) conducted a population-based study that included 989 incident cases (30–79 years of age at diagnosis) from Chicago, US. They found that airborne Cd was significantly and positively associated with an increased risk of developing ER-/PR-, but not ER+ /PR+ breast tumors. Liu et al. (2015) reported that long-term airborne exposure to low doses of Cd was associated with hormone receptor-negative (ER-/PR-) breast tumors in women who had never smoked and who had not moved from California, US. White et al. (2019) enrolled 2587 cases of BC diagnosed with an average of 7.4 years of follow-up from the US. They found a significantly higher risk of BC in postmenopausal women comparing the highest and lowest Cd quintiles. Also, the association for BC risk with airborne Cd levels was stronger in women who were overweight/obese with a BMI ≥ 25 and who were also current smokers, but without statistical significance.

Although few studies have looked at the impact of airborne Cd on the

risk of developing BC, it is important to emphasize three things. First, due to the lack of historical data on the emission of air pollutants, including Cd, it is difficult to reconstruct past exposures. Second, in case-control study designs, control is itself debatable. Third, studies that included ER/PR status, cancer stage, and histopathological types of BC usually suffer from incomplete information for all study participants, which affect statistical analysis and leads to errors.

5. Conclusion

In summary, this up-to-date review analysis demonstrates that environmental Cd has a deleterious impact on breast homeostasis. *In vitro* and *in vivo* studies strongly show the harmful effects of Cd on breast health. We found that Cd could be responsible for the development and progression of malignant breast tumors according to the significantly higher levels of Cd in clinical matrices of cases (blood, urine, breast tissue, keratin materials) than in the same clinical matrices of controls. Cadmium does not appear to affect BC density. On the other hand, Cd has a detrimental effect on sex hormones, disrupting the balance of estrogen and androgen. Depending on the primary exposure to Cd, studies looking at dietary Cd intake and BC risk by measuring Cd in urine or blood generally support this association. In marked contrast, studies looking at dietary Cd intake and BC risk generally (but not by measuring urine or blood Cd) do not support this association. The effect of airborne Cd on BC risk was weak but could be associated with specific histological forms, primarily ER-/PR- invasive tubular breast carcinomas. Overall, although a cause-and-effect relationship between Cd and BC cannot be established at this time, future well-designed research (prospective and retrospective human studies, mechanistic/biochemical, and other studies) is certainly needed and should be supported, as it is evident that Cd could be a risk factor for malignant breast tumors. Cadmium levels should be measured and studied in each clinical matrix separately; analyzing combined Cd levels from multiple clinical matrices as a single group is scientifically unjustified. Another suggestion is to quantify MTs, Zn, Ca, and Fe along with Cd, to complete the analysis and obtain key data. In the meantime, to prevent unnecessary exposure to Cd and thus avoid its adverse effects, particularly in Cd-vulnerable groups, we suggest individuals avoid Cd-contaminated foods, stop smoking, and use indoor air purifiers, while industrial hygiene needs to be improved on a large scale to protect human health worldwide.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Manojlović Dragan: Writing – review & editing. **Ščančar Janez:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Stojsavljević Aleksandar:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Aničić Radomir:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Zeković Milica:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Kocić Milan:** Writing – review & editing. **Gluvić Zoran:** Writing – review & editing.

Authors' contributions

RA, MZ, and AS wrote the first draft of the manuscript; RA, MZ, MK, ZG, DM, and JŠ participated in subsequent editing and reviewing of the manuscript; AS participated in the conceptualization, supervision, writing, editing, and reviewing of the manuscript. All authors provided critical feedback and revisions, ultimately granting their final approval for publication.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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